

Project Title	Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice
Project Acronym	WorldFAIR
Grant Agreement No	101058393
Instrument	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01
Topic, type of action	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41 HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	24 months
Project Website	http://worldfair-project.eu

D8.2 Urban Health Data - Learning and training

Work Package	WP08 – Urban Health
Lead Author (Org)	Usama Bilal (Urban Health Collaborative – Drexel University)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Ran Li (Urban Health Collaborative – Drexel University); Ana Ortigoza (Urban Health Collaborative – Drexel University, PAHO); Theresa Anderson (CODATA Consultant)

Due Date	31.03.2024
Date	21.03.2024
Version	1.0 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731625

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	22.02.2024	Ran Li, Usama Bilal, Ana Ortigoza, Theresa Anderson	First Draft for internal review
0.2	28.02.2024	Ran Li, Usama Bilal, Ana Ortigoza	Final internal draft for WorldFAIR review
0.3	14.03.2024	Max Rünzel (reviewer), Steve McEachern (reviewer)	Reviewer comments included
0.4	20.03.2024	Ran Li, Usama Bilal, Ana Ortigoza	Second draft following WorldFAIR review
1	21.03.2024	Laura Molloy (editor)	Copyedit and finalised version

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WorldFAIR has received funding from the European Commission's WIDERA coordination and support programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101058393. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to control, Respect, Ethics
CEDAR	CEDAR Workbench (https://metadatacenter.org/)
CHOP	Children’s Hospital of Philadelphia
COMPASS	Community Partnerships to Advance Science for Society
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
ESCALA	Urban Health and Climate Change in Informal Settlements in Latin America Study
NIH DMS	NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy
PAHO	Pan American Health Organization
PDPH	Philadelphia Department of Public Health
SALURBAL	Salud Urbana en América Latina (Urban Health in Latin America)
UHC	Urban Health Collaborative, Drexel University

Executive summary

WorldFAIR Deliverable 8.2 “Urban Health Data - Learning and training” aims to describe efforts from WorldFAIR WP08 to create a community of practice in FAIR and CARE principles for urban health, train this community of practice, and show improvements in our own implementation of the FAIR principles in our work. This deliverable has two key parts: 1) describing a training course we developed in June 2023 on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to control, Respect, and Ethics) principles and an activity we are conducting in May 2024 to bring together the local FAIR/CARE community in Philadelphia (and beyond); and 2) an updated FAIR implementation profile as part of the SALURBAL (Salud Urbana en América Latina - Urban Health in Latin America) project.

In the first part, we describe our inaugural course, "How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR", conducted 26-30 June 2023 with ten participants. The course aimed to bridge gaps in understanding the FAIR and CARE principles. We found an increase in participants’ knowledge and emerging interests in the topics through pre- and post-course surveys¹. The course encountered challenges in exemplifying the FAIR and CARE principles in practical urban health settings, highlighting a need for improved materials that clearly illustrate how to operationalise these principles. Moving forward, the Urban Health Collaborative is organising a series of activities in May 2024 to continue developing a community of practice around these principles. These include roundtable discussions, webinars, and interviews with project leaders, aimed at refining training materials and fostering a culture of continued education and support in data management and stewardship. This will include a keynote lecture by Dr. Theresa Anderson that will be livestreamed to the WorldFAIR community.

Our updated FAIR Implementation Profile describes our efforts to harmonise multi-country urban health data, aiming to create a machine-actionable resource that aligns with the FAIR principles. This initiative represents a critical step in addressing the data management complexities of urban health research, offering a pragmatic approach to the harmonisation of extensive datasets across various countries and domains. We summarise the project journey through the development and implementation of a data engineering initiative. We detail the use of data engineering techniques such as Dimensional Modelling and One Big Table to manage and organise data, making it accessible and efficient for analysis. In updating upon WorldFAIR Deliverable 8.1 here, we connect the project’s specific challenges to the broader goal of establishing a robust, FAIR-compliant data infrastructure in urban health research. Finally, we introduce the SALURBAL portal, a user-friendly interface designed to facilitate public access to the project's harmonised data. This portal is expected to serve as a model for similar initiatives,

¹ Available at <https://zenodo.org/records/10231435>

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promoting the principles of FAIR data management and underlining the potential benefits of such approaches in urban health and beyond.

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1. Introduction

The purpose of WorldFAIR Work Package 08 is to advance the FAIR and CARE principles (Wilkinson 2016; Russo Carroll 2021) in the practices of Urban Health research. In Deliverable 8.1 “Urban Health Data - Guidelines and Recommendations” (Ortigoza et al 2023), we presented the implementation of the FAIR principles in Urban Health Research. These guidelines and recommendations and other work on the CARE principles carried out by SALURBAL informed the development of training materials and the design of activities among population health researchers with the objective of generating a community of practice that supports the understanding and implementation of the FAIR and CARE principles in Urban Health.

In the present deliverable D8.2 “Urban Health Data - Learning and training”, Part 1 has two components:

(1A) materials and lessons learned from the training course “*How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and good practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/ public health*”; and

(1B) a plan for engagement activities oriented to create a community of practice among different organisations, researchers, and practitioners working in Urban Health across the Americas.

Additionally, in Part 2 of the current document, we provide an updated description of the FAIR implementation profile (FIP) carried out by the SALURBAL team during the elaboration of a data platform that contains all the data and information produced by the SALURBAL project.

2. Part 1: Learning and training activities – lessons learned and prospective engagement activities.

During 26-30 June 2023, the course “How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and good practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/public health” was taught as part of the Summer Course series at the Urban Health Collaborative-Drexel University², partially in response to the demand

² <https://drexel.edu/uhc/>

created by NIH grant applications and grant renewals for help to generate robust and detailed data management and sharing plans (NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy 2023).

This course was the first of its kind to be offered within the Dornsife School of Public Health to a wide range of audiences in public health, data science, and urban health research. Materials, implementation experience, and further recommendations are described in section 2.1.

Beyond the success of the course, lessons learned from this first experience are considered for strategically planning a greater and broader recruitment of participants in a next iteration of this course during June 2024. Additionally, a set of activities oriented to the dissemination of FAIR and CARE principles and the establishing of a community of practice are planned to take place during 13-17 May 2024. During these activities we expect to consult with key stakeholders in data stewardship and research about the training materials designed, improve the quality of the training content, and customise materials to the needs of the audience. A detailed plan for engagement activities and the potential creation of a community of practice are described in section 2.2.

2.1 Training course in FAIR and CARE principles for researchers and practitioners in urban health: materials, course implementation and further recommendations

2.1.1 Course motivation and goals

The motivation for the creation of the course ‘How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and best practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/ public health’ came from the apparent fragmentation and heterogeneity in the understanding of FAIR and CARE principles among researchers and practitioners in Urban Health. The Urban Health discipline faces many challenges related to data due to:

- a) its complex nature of interconnected knowledges and practices, such as the need for a common vocabulary (i.e., how we define urban areas, informal settlements);
- b) the use of data from different sources (i.e., place based and spatial data, health registries); and
- c) the creation of data that could be comparable across urban areas and over time (i.e. accounting for differences between cities and within cities over time), among others [Quistberg 2019].

The understanding of FAIR and CARE principles could improve data documentation practices and standardisation as well as more ethical use of the many sources of data involved.

The overall purpose of this course was to provide participants with a broad understanding of the FAIR and CARE principles that could help them to design and develop data management plans for research-based and community-based projects. More specifically the goals of the course included:

1. Understand concepts and frameworks related to FAIR and CARE principles in Open Science.
2. Recognise and compare challenges in FAIR and CARE implementation within the Urban Health discipline.
3. Identify components and requirements of data management plan development.
4. Develop critical acumen on the assessment of strengths and weaknesses of data management plans, and the impacts and benefits of FAIR and CARE data principles implementation.

2.1.2 Course structure

The course involved 15 hours total for 5 days. Modality included, for each day, the delivery of remote asynchronous pre-recorded self-paced lectures (~1.5 hours) and then a remote synchronous (or in-person) discussion and/or practical session (~ 1.5 hours). From day 2 onwards, there was practical time each day in which participants integrated concepts and practice, building towards the completion and discussion of the data management plans that were presented at the end of the course (i.e. on day 5). The course schedule and content are available in the Appendix. A pre- and post-course survey was conducted to understand the level of knowledge participants had about FAIR and CARE principles in advance of the course and how that changed after attending it (pre- and post-course survey models are available in the Appendix).

2.1.3 Audience

The target audience was intended to include people from many disciplines including public health, health care, and data science, as well as public health practitioners working with data in community projects. No prerequisites were required. A total of 10 participants attended the course. One participant was involved in academic research and the rest of the group were from the Philadelphia Department of Public Health. Most of them referred to frequently working in data collection and processing of secondary sources, using data for monitoring and research, or having responsibility for stewarding data (Figure 1).

Results from the pre- course survey showed that there was very low to low knowledge of FAIR and

CARE principles as well as in metadata schemas and preservation policies, in advance of the course (Figure 2). After the course, the overall perception of participants showed a deeper understanding of these concepts (Figure 3). There was an increased interest in connecting with instructors after the course with the consequent creation by participants of a Slack channel that included all participants and instructors. The channel was active during the weeks after the course, but the level of engagement diminished over time, partially due to a lack of continuity in supporting the training platform and resources beyond the duration of the Drexel Summer Institute.

2.1.4 Challenges arising

A challenge seen throughout the course was the exemplification of FAIR and CARE principles or whether participants could find ways of operationalising these principles in their everyday work and in each instance of the data cycle. This feedback by participants helped to improve the materials to better identify and incorporate such examples in the next round of the course, which will be shared and consulted in a series of activities planned for community engagement (see section 2.2).

Another limitation of the course was the low interest among academics. One of the reasons for low attendance among researchers and academic faculty members using primary or secondary data for quantitative research can be attributed to the mistaken belief that these topics are not key or central in their work but mostly matter to data managers / data scientists. In the next iteration of the course, we plan to incorporate advocacy materials drawing attention to, for example, the NIH requirements and the benefits of the FAIR and CARE principles. These materials will be also validated during the activities described in section 2.2.

2.1.5 Reflection on the course

Overall, the course was successful in providing content on FAIR and CARE principles to an audience that surprisingly did not belong to the academic context. This course was unique to the curricula of the Urban Health Collaborative and other research institutions in public health, having the potential to increase recruitment and scope of participants in future rounds. The creation of a communication channel, as an initiative originated among participants, showed the need for spaces that provide continued educational opportunities as well as technical support and advice. Part of this gap is planned to be addressed with the activities described in section 2.2. These activities may also improve involvement of the academic audience; the majority of those working with Urban Health data.

Figure 1. Frequency and /or likelihood of performing data- related tasks at work. Footnote: Axis X shows the frequency of responses across the 10 participants ; Axis Y shows the frequency or likelihood of performing the tasks described with coloured bars.

Figure 2. Level of knowledge, experience, and/or familiarity with FAIR and CARE – related concepts before the course. Footnote: Axis X shows the number of participants (total = 10 respondents); Axis Y shows the level of knowledge/ expertise/ familiarity of participants with concepts described with coloured bars.

Figure 3. Level of knowledge, experience, and/or familiarity with FAIR and CARE – related concepts after the course. Footnote: Axis X shows the number of participants (total = 10 respondents); Axis Y shows the level of knowledge/ expertise/ familiarity of participants with concepts described with coloured bars.

2.2 Towards the creation of a community of practice

Lessons learned from the training course, “How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and best practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/ public health”, helped us to identify gaps in content and audience reach, and to identify modalities to connect content and audience.

As a result, we are planning a series of activities to integrate the FAIR and CARE principles in ways that can be applied to large-scale, cross-domain projects; and to engage teams in these projects for the development of a community of practice in Urban Health that could provide further connectivity and exchange of experience. Table 1, below, summarises the goals, participants and audience, and expected outputs for these activities.

We propose four key activities:

1. *‘Round Table 1’* will focus on the presentation of local data stewardship case studies, where we seek to expand the discussion on FAIR implementation to the concrete challenges in data integration, standardisation, and reuse, faced by the invited projects.
2. *‘Round Table 2’* is intended to revisit the processes of abstraction throughout the lifecycles of data collection and analysis, through the lens of the CARE principles; and to discuss the vulnerability of data to misinterpretation, misuse, and misappropriation when ethical dimensions related to data provenance and integrity are not considered.
3. The *seminar / webinar* on ethical considerations in the use of artificial intelligence could shed further light on current and potential concerns regarding transparency, integrity, equity and ethics towards minorities and vulnerable populations in the implementation of open data. We will stream this activity live for the entire WorldFAIR community.

The experiences shared by participants during these activities can then be integrated as practical examples in the educational materials developed for the training course.

4. *‘Small-group interviews’* with leaders and participants from relevant projects will also help to discuss more closely how to refine and adapt the educational materials developed for the training course to the characteristics and needs of different identified audiences. Additional one-to-one conversations with key academic stakeholders (Table 1) would help to engage Urban and Public Health researchers and practitioners in a community of practice. These include engagement with research projects at Drexel and in other institutions in Philadelphia that use urban health data, but for whom the use of the FAIR or CARE principles may still not be pervasive.

By connecting initiatives on data management and stewardship across borders, while raising awareness of the way cultures of counting can contribute to downstream discrimination and bias in data globalisation, we hope to contribute to the creation of this community of practice. This ultimately can contribute to mobilising efforts to improve processes of collection and registration that make data more valuable and useful for decision-making.

The projects and participants that will be involved in these activities are described in Table 2. Some projects that have been invited to participate are led by scholars in the Urban Health Collaborative (SALURBAL³, ESCALA⁴), while in other projects (ComPASS⁵, Pan-Diaspora⁶) the UHC is a partnership of a bigger consortium. Additionally, other organisations and projects such as Data 4 Equity, PhilaStats⁷, and the MetaData Research Center⁸ have vision and scope of works similar to UHC-based projects, and have potential for future partnerships. Many of these projects work with secondary sources of data (e.g., SALURBAL, Data 4 Equity, Phila Stats), while others are mainly focused in primary collection data and generation of new data (e.g., ESCALA; ComPASS). With this diverse audience invited to participate in multiple activities, we expect to cover multiple user profiles with different needs, which will help us to better tailor educational and training material on FAIR and CARE.

³ <https://drexel.edu/lac/salurbal/overview/>

⁴ <https://drexel.edu/uhc/about/News/2023/March/Lacuna-grant-announcement/>

⁵ <https://drexel.edu/news/archive/2023/September/Dornsife-School-of-Public-Health-Award-for-NIH-Health-Equity-Program>

⁶ https://drexel.edu/~media/Files/lac/Publications/Race_Racism_Data-Brief_ENG_v2.ashx?la=en

⁷ <https://www.phila.gov/departments/department-of-public-health/data/philadelphia-vital-statistics/>

⁸ <https://mrc.cci.drexel.edu/>

Table 1. Summary of outreach activities for the generation of a FAIR and CARE community of practice in Urban Health

Goal	Engagement tactics and activities	Participants and Audience	Expected outputs/ products
Goal 1. Expand knowledge and discussion among researchers and practitioners in Urban Health on the implementation of FAIR and CARE principles	<i>Round table 1:</i> Discussion on challenges in the implementation of Urban Health data platforms and opportunities for improvement through the implementation of FAIR principles	Presenters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WorldFAIR - WP08 - SALURBAL^a data portal - UHC^b portal - PDPH^c -PhilaStats portal Audience: Open to public in the Philadelphia area	Identification of gaps in the understanding and implementation of FAIR principles. Case studies on FAIR implementation that can be used as exemplifying material during the second (i.e. June 2024) iteration of the Summer Course
	<i>Round table 2:</i> The importance of data provenance and governance in data stewardship and the potential of CARE principles to support and improve these processes.	Presenters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WorldFAIR WP08 - ComPASS Project^d - Ubuntu- Pan-Diaspora project - Drexel Metadata Center - PAHO^e Audience: Open to public in the Philadelphia area	Identification of gaps in the understanding and implementation of CARE principles. Case studies on CARE implementation that can be used as exemplifying material during the second (i.e. June 2024) iteration of the Summer Course
	<i>Weekly Forum Seminar</i> on Data Ethics in Artificial Intelligence (Keynote speaker + discussion)	Presenters: WorldFAIR WP08 (Theresa Anderson, CODATA consultant)	Document notes on appreciation of further challenges related to FAIR and CARE principles in using data for artificial intelligence that can be used as additional content during the second (i.e. June 2024) iteration of the Summer Course.

		Audience: open to the public, with participants worldwide engaging remotely. A registration link will be shared with the WorldFAIR community.	
Goal 2. Fostering a community of practice in Urban Health research and practice	<i>'Small-group interviews'</i> between WorldFAIR members and UHC project partners and other relevant individuals or projects in the area	Participants: COMPASS Project (Amy Carroll-Scott/Jan Eberth) SALURBAL DMC (Kari Moore) UBUNTU (Jen Ware) UHC UHC Research and Data Core (Loni Tabb) ESCALA ^f (Alex Quistberg) PDPH ^c /PhilaStats Team (Megan Todd) CHOP ^g – Arcus team (Julianna Pakstis) Dr Jane Greenberg (Metadata Center- ISchool)	Advocacy material on FAIR and CARE relevance in the Urban Health research and practice.

Key: a) SALURBAL = Urban Health in Latin America project (Salud Urbana en América Latina); b) UHC= Urban Health Collaborative; c) PDPH = Philadelphia Department of Public Health; d) Community Partnerships to Advance Science for Society (CompPASS); e) PAHO = Pan American Health Organization; f) ESCALA = Urban Health and Climate Change in Informal Settlements in Latin America Study; g) CHOP = Children’s Hospital of Philadelphia.

Table 2. Summary of organisations involved in the discussion and engagement activities

Description of projects and organisations involved	Organisation team lead (s)
The Urban Health Collaborative Research and Data Core supports work that characterises health in cities and conducts research on health determinants and the impact of policies. It is starting to implement some FAIR principles in its data management.	Dr Loni Tabb, Kari Moore, Matt Jannetti
The Data and Methods Core of the SALURBAL project is the hub for the organisation and compilation of data across the entire project (15 institutions across the Americas). Among other things, it has coordinated the creation of a data portal following the FAIR principles (see Part 2: FAIR implementation Profile, in the current deliverable).	Kari Moore, Usama Bilal, Ana Diez Roux
The CompPASS project at Drexel enables research at 25 community-serving institutions that address underlying structural factors within communities that affect health - often referred to as social determinants of health - such as access to education, healthy food, employment, transportation, and health care. Among other things, the CompPASS project is organising a data stewardship commission to ensure that data generated by communities continues being owned by these communities.	Dr Amy Carroll-Scott- and Dr. Jan Eberth
The Pan-Diaspora project aims to map the current state of knowledge on race- and ethnicity-based data in the context of racial health inequalities across 22 Latin American countries between 2000- 2023. It is coordinated by the Ubuntu Center at Drexel and McGill University in Canada.	Dr Mabel Caraballi
Data4 Equity is a project of the Pan American Health Organization to support statistical offices in Latin American countries in the incorporation of gender diversity, ethnicity, and other dimensions involving minority groups in health information systems.	Dr Ana Ortigoza
The ESCALA project will collect neighbourhood-level data, street-level images, and audio recordings from citizen scientists to provide a rich dataset that links environmental and social characteristics, climate data, and health outcomes. The team will also provide data from Bogotá and Barranquilla's informal settlements – traditionally under-researched areas that face disproportionately high exposure to climate hazards compared to other urban neighbourhoods.	Dr Alex Quitsberg

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<p>PhilaStats is the new home of Philadelphia's vital statistics data, coordinated by the Philadelphia Department of Public Health. This dashboard highlights statistics and trends in natality (births), mortality (deaths), and population for Philadelphia residents between 2011 and 2019.</p>	<p>Dr. Megan Todd</p>
<p>The Metadata Research Center, located at the College of Computing & Informatics (CCI), Drexel University, leads and innovates metadata solutions for pressing information/data-oriented challenges.</p>	<p>Dr Jane Greenber</p>

3. Part 2: Improved FAIR implementation profile (FIP)

3.1 Introduction

In WorldFAIR Deliverable 8.1⁹, the urban health project SALURBAL documented, firstly, the process of harmonising multi-country and multi-domain data within a single project and, secondly, a proposal¹⁰ for a data engineering initiative (FAIR Implementation Plan, or 'FIP') to make this harmonised data resource machine-actionable. This section of D8.2 aims to contextualise our FIP through the controlled vocabulary of data engineering, give insights on challenges/adaptations during implementation, share the final user-facing product, and share some lessons and insights for the future.

In the current Deliverable, we will aim to be technically accurate in how we describe our implementation details in data engineering terms to enable external facing experts to understand our process and also to start introducing fundamental data engineering concepts that may aid other urban health researchers who endeavour to scale similarly complex and comprehensive urban health harmonisation efforts. To this end, we start with a primer on data engineering for public health.

3.2 Data engineering primer for Urban Health

3.2.1 Data engineering as a framework for addressing FAIR challenges in Urban Health

In the SALURBAL project, researchers encountered challenges associated with managing and harmonising extensive datasets that spanned various countries, time frames, and data sources. These challenges encompassed the sheer volume of data, the complexity of harmonising disparate datasets across different geographical and temporal dimensions, and the necessity for data to be machine-actionable for automated processes such as distribution, analytics, and codebook generation. The project's data management complexities were further compounded by the need to coordinate multidisciplinary data workgroups across diverse national and skill backgrounds, highlighting the critical demand for an efficient and scalable approach to the implementation of FAIR in urban health research.

Approaching these challenges was difficult for our project as we primarily have backgrounds in statistics, epidemiology, and public health, but throughout the FIP process we have learned that

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10231137>

¹⁰ <https://drexel-uhc.github.io/salurbal-project-dashboard/>

data engineering is a core skill set for FAIR implementation across the Urban Health domain. To that end, it is of value to contextualise not only our FAIR challenges but also our FIP within the frame of data engineering.

3.2.2 What is Data Engineering?

The definition of Data Engineering (DE) as a field and role is constantly changing (see Table 3 for a simplification of its history into periods, and the skills on which those periods focused). DE started in the 1980s, focusing on small data sets and SQL in relational databases to enable business analytics. The web boom introduced the need for Big Data management, prompting a shift to distributed computing (e.g. Hadoop or Spark) and the birth of the Big Data Engineer role. The cloud revolution further expanded the role's focus to include cloud technologies, leading to the adoption of cloud databases; the role of Big Data Engineer didn't change in name but shifted focus to cloud infrastructure. Eventually, around 2017, it turned out that everything is big data, and so the term was simplified to just 'data engineer' (Späti 2024).

Table 3. History context summary of the field of data engineering

Time period	Skill		Infrastructure		
	Analytics	Data Modelling	Relational Databases	Distributed Systems	Cloud Infrastructure
1980's - 2000's (SQL + small data)	X	X	X		
2000 - 2010 (Web boom + big data)	X	X		X	
2010 - 2015 (Cloud Revolution)	X	X			X
~2017 to present (Data Engineering)	X	X	X	X	X

So back to the question: what is Data Engineering? Despite the evolution of data engineering, there are some timeless recurring concepts we can use to define the field. Based on Table 3 - where common concepts are highlighted in bold - we can say that data engineering is a field that is focused on enabling efficient **analytics** (deriving insight from data, otherwise known as research) by

designing efficient **data modelling** of flows from raw to end-users and effectively expressing that design with the appropriate **infrastructure** - whether it be relational databases, distributed systems, or cloud infrastructure.

In the context of FAIR and Urban Health, analytics is the research aspect, and the FAIR implementation falls into data modelling and infrastructure. However, infrastructure is organisation-specific whereas the semantics of how data flows is generalisable and infrastructure-agnostic.

We will focus on explaining FAIR implementation for the SALURBAL project through data modelling, specifically focusing on two techniques particularly amenable for large urban health projects like SALUBAL: Dimensional Modelling, and One Big Table. Below we introduce these concepts. Appendix 6.3 contains some useful definitions.

3.2.3 Data modelling

Data modelling is a critical process in managing and utilising data effectively, particularly in Urban Health where the design of an organisation's flow of data can significantly influence the pace of research synthesis. It involves creating a structured framework that represents an organisation's data, detailing how different pieces of information are interconnected and flow within a system. These data model designs are commonly visualised in the form of an Entity-Relationship Diagram (ERD). Below, we will first introduce two key techniques for data modelling and then contextualise these within the scope of other data modelling techniques.

To make these techniques a little more concrete we will show how an example dataset could be represented in different data models. The example dataset contains information on hospital visits with some basic information about the patient and visit instance. We can introduce this in the most intuitive data modelling technique known as 'One Big Table'.

3.2.3.1 One Big Table (OBT)

Of all data modelling techniques, One Big Table (OBT) is the technique that focuses most on storing data in the most accessible and efficient format for the end user. It consolidates all data into a single table, simplifying data access for researchers so they do not have to understand the data model to understand what tables they want and then use a database to write queries to perform those joins. For example, Figure 4 (below) shows how our example set of hospitalisation data can be stored in a single table.

In this table, each row is a record, and information on that record is stored ‘wide’ (one column per variable, as opposed to ‘long’, where one column contains variable names). OBT removes the complexities of relationships between tables by storing data redundantly; this makes the structure easily understandable by end-users and interoperable with downstream applications (i.e., research with statistical software, dashboards, and web applications).

PublicHealthData		
int	VisitID	PK
int	PatientID	
string	PatientName	
date	DOB	
string	Gender	
string	Address	
int	ICD10	
string	DiseaseName	
string	DiseaseCategory	
date	VisitDate	
string	DayOfWeek	
string	Month	
int	Year	
int	FacilityID	

Figure 4. Example Entity Relation Diagram for an OBT data model.

3.2.3.2 Dimensional modelling

Dimensional modelling is another analytics/user-oriented data modelling approach where we break the data up into ‘facts’ (data) and ‘dimensions’ (metadata) (Kimball 2013). Fact tables contain quantitative metrics or the actual data you will use for analysis; each row is an instance of a process on which you want to have information. Dimension tables provide descriptive context to the numeric measures in the fact tables, which essentially means metadata.

Although there are multiple tables as opposed to the One Big Table approach, the dimensional model design process - in which there is a formal four-step design process - ensures that the structure of your tables is not only intuitive to understand by the end-user (researchers) but also effectively stores your data in a way that facilitates easy data retrieval; these two characteristics make it an effective data modelling approach for research.

To make this a little more concrete; let's go through the dimensional model design with our example healthcare data.

- Step 1: Selecting a process to analyse

The process we'll focus on is **patient healthcare visits**. This process involves patients visiting healthcare facilities for diagnosis and treatment, capturing critical data points like patient demographics, disease information, treatment effectiveness, and facility details.

- Step 2: Declaring the data grain

The grain of this dataset is "a single patient visits a healthcare facility." This means each record in our dataset represents one instance of a patient visiting a facility, including all relevant details about the visit (e.g., patient ID, disease diagnosed, date of visit, facility visited, length of stay, and treatment effectiveness).

- Step 3: Identify the dimensions

Based on the business process and declared grain, the dimension tables identified in this dataset are:

- DIM_Patient: Contains attributes related to the patient, such as PatientID, PatientName, DOB, Gender, and Address.
- DIM_Disease: Includes details about the disease diagnosed during the visit, characterized by ICD10 codes, DiseaseName, and DiseaseCategory.
- DIM_Date: Captures temporal details of the visit, including VisitDate, DayOfWeek, Month, and Year.
- DIM_Facility: Holds information about the healthcare facility where the visit occurred, such as FacilityID, FacilityName, and FacilityType.

These dimensions provide the descriptive context around each patient visit, allowing for multifaceted analysis across different aspects of the healthcare process.

- Step 4: Identifying the facts

The facts in this dataset, centred around the FACT_PatientVisits table, are quantitative measures that can be analysed:

- NumberOfVisits (if aggregated from multiple records): Though not explicitly mentioned in the initial table, it can be derived or used in analysis to count visits per patient, disease, or facility.
- LengthOfStay: A numerical measure indicating the duration of the patient's stay in the facility during the visit.
- TreatmentEffectiveness: A quantitative assessment of the treatment's success, potentially scored or rated based on predefined criteria.

These facts provide measurable outcomes and key performance indicators that can be analysed about the descriptive dimensions, allowing healthcare providers and analysts to extract insights about patient care, disease management, and facility utilisation.

After going through this formalised process for dimensional model design we have now clarified our design which can be represented visually in Figure 5. This diagram shows us how our fact table and dimension tables interact with each other. While the information is split apart into separate tables, the way it is intuitively split into fact (i.e., data on visit) and dimension (i.e., additional context) facilitates user understanding and enables retrieval of data required for analysis.

Figure 5. Example Entity Relation Diagram for a dimensional modelling design.

3.2.3.3 Data modelling landscape

We have now introduced two techniques for data modelling. One Big Table (OBT) stores all information about your process of interest in a single table. Dimensional modelling organises your process of interest into a fact table (i.e., data) and dimension tables (i.e., context/metadata).

However, these are just two of the many data modelling techniques that are used by data engineers to organise and present data for analytics. We won't go into them in detail but it is important to understand the context of these methods in terms of complexity which is often measured in terms of a normalization vs. denormalization scale.

Figure 6. Data modelling techniques on a normalization vs. denormalization scale.

3.2.3.4 Normalization

Normalization aims to minimise data redundancy by ensuring that each piece of data is stored only once. In this approach, data relationships are maintained through references, such as foreign keys. This method is depicted on the left side in Figure 6 and is characterised by a highly structured design that eliminates duplication. Techniques include traditional relational modelling (3NF) and Data Vaults (DV).

Advantages:

- Reduces data redundancy, potentially leading to smaller storage requirements.
- Offers flexibility in database design, allowing Data Engineers to create complex relational structures as needed.

- Optimised for transactional database operations.

Disadvantages:

- Requires management of a complex schema and relationships between tables, including all associated keys.
- Less accessible to individuals without data engineering or SQL expertise.
- May result in slower query performance for large datasets.

3.2.3.5 Denormalization

Denormalization embraces data redundancy by allowing nested and redundant data structures. This approach is illustrated on the right side in Figure 6. The OBT technique is a highly denormalized approach where in scenarios like hospitalisation records where a patient may have multiple visits, patient information (e.g., Name, Address) is redundantly stored across many rows.

Advantages:

- Simplifies data structure by consolidating data into a single table, enhancing simplicity.
- Facilitates analytics by providing a straightforward data model for analysis.
- Enhances accessibility for end-users, requiring no SQL or database expertise for data retrieval.
- Offers fast query performance for big data, designed to reflect intuitive ways of structuring research or analytics data.

Disadvantages:

- Increases file sizes due to redundant data. (However, this may be offset by using modern columnar storage solutions designed for analytic data like Apache Parquet - see section 3.7 for a definition of the .parquet data format).
- Updates can be challenging, necessitating careful handling of upstream joins.

3.3 Contextualising our D8.1 FIP proposal

In WorldFAIR Deliverable D8.1¹¹, we drafted a proposal for moving SALURBAL into a higher level of FAIR which had two phases: 1) FAIR implementation within the project and 2) building a public-facing web interface for our FAIRified data resource. Here, this section will focus on clarifying

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10231137>

the first phase - local FAIR implementation - by describing it with the data engineering vocabulary introduced above before we talk about the process and future insights.

The SALURBAL project FAIR implementation process involves building infrastructure that enables machines to be able to find/access/operate on SALURBAL data/metadata at the data point level. This process was operationalised at two levels: dataset-level dimensional modelling and project-level One Big Table.

3.3.1 Dataset level - Dimensional modelling

3.3.1.1 Generalisable dimensional model design

We start with the most fundamental unit being utilised in the SALURBAL dataset. Let's go through the dimensional model design process (Kimball 2013).

- Step 1: Selecting a process to analyse

The process we'll focus on is a single SALURBAL data point; this enables us to manage data flow according to original Data Use Agreements (DUA) and automate the generation of higher-level artefacts such as codebooks, analytic datasets, and dashboard inputs.

- Step 2: Declaring the data grain

The grain of this design is “a single data point per dataset, variable identifier, per strata, time interval, the geographic identifier.” This means each row in our fact table represents one data point that comes from a dataset, for a specific variable, for specific strata if applicable (e.g. male or female or specific age group), for a specific time interval (e.g. 2010 or Sep 1, 2010) and for a specific geographic unit (SALURBAL level and SALURBAL id). This level of atomicity allows us to capture the diversity of SALURBAL data. Specific grain columns include:

- Dataset ID
- Variable ID
- Strata ID
- Geographic ID
- Country
- Geographic level
- Year
- Month

- Day
- Step 3: Identify the dimensions

Based on the process and declared grain, the dimensions (i.e., metadata fields or important context) about the data stored in the fact table we want to capture include:

- Domain: The highest level of variable categorization such as “Built Environment.”
- Subdomain: A lower level of variable categorization than domain, such as “Transportation.”
- Variable Label: A short, human-readable label for the variable.
- Variable Definition: A detailed definition of the variable.
- Value Type: The type of data the variable represents, such as integer, float, categorical ... etc.
- Units: Unit of the value, such as percent or cases per 100k.
- Coding: Describe the coding scheme if the value is categorical.
- Strata Description: Description of data strata.
- Source: The source of the data.
- Dataset Notes: Additional information or dataset/file-specific notes.
- Limitations: Descriptions of any limitations for the variable.
- Acknowledgments: Any acknowledgments for the variable.
- Longitudinal: Indicates whether the variable is suitable for longitudinal analysis
- Public: A categorical field defining the accessibility of this data point to internal, and external users.

These dimensions provide the descriptive context around each data point that not just gives context for users but also allows internal systems to automate data/metadata distribution.

- Step 4: Identifying the facts

The facts in the fact (data) table are quantitative measures that can be analysed. Note that for some data points, not all facts are relevant and available.

- Value of the data point
- Upper confidence interval
- Lower confidence interval
- Iteration number

These facts provide the various aspects of a single data point that facilitate users to access the various facets that are relevant to their analysis.

3.3.2 Dataset-specific implementation

The challenging aspect of dimensional modelling design for SALURBAL is that while the dimensional attributes (metadata fields) are standard across the whole project, the structure of that metadata - as expressed in dimension tables - varies across datasets; in other words, the relationship between the metadata (stored in dimension tables) and data (stored in fact tables) differs across datasets. This largely stems from the fact that dimensional attributes often reflect information about raw data sources, which are harmonised into SALURBAL datasets, and the complexity of raw data sources vary dramatically across SALURBAL datasets. Because the structure of dimension tables reflect harmonisation complexity, different levels of complexity across datasets means that how dimension tables are operationalised will also differ by dataset.

In some simpler cases, we have a single data source that we can use to derive a dataset for many countries and years. However, in more complex cases, we can have multiple data sources (from varying countries or years) that are harmonised to produce a single SALURBAL dataset; and all shades of this complexity in between. Because of this varied complexity and relationship between the fact table (data) and dimension tables (metadata) across datasets, it is not possible to have a standard dimension model design that works for every SALURBAL dataset. To accommodate this complexity, we utilise our generalised dimensional model design as a starting point for dataset-specific implementations which allow flexibility in how dimension tables are operationalised to best capture a standardised list of dimensional attributes for each dataset. Let's see how this looks for two case study datasets.

3.3.2.1 Simple dataset: Air Pollution

The SALURBAL Air Pollution dataset is a rather simple example where all harmonised SALURBAL data come from a single original dataset. This means that the interaction between the metadata tables (i.e., dimensional tables) and data table (i.e., fact table) is quite straightforward. In fact, when we look at the diagram (Figure 7) of the dimensional design for this dataset (shown below) we can see that all the dimensional attributes of these datasets can be captured in just two dimension tables:

- 1) The 'by_dataset' dimensional table which captures context on the dataset level. Notice how source and all associated context (e.g., limitations of the data, whether the data can be

publicly displayed, etc.) can be captured at the dataset level because this dataset only has a single source.

2) The 'by_variable' dimension table which captures context at the variable level.

Figure 7. Entity relationship diagram for a SALURBAL dataset that has a 'simple' harmonisation process.

3.3.2.2. Complex dataset - Life Expectancy

The Life Expectancy dataset is one of the more complex SALURBAL datasets. The harmonisation involved getting population and death information from 10 different countries individually and then modelling them to produce cross-sectional age and sex-specific life estimates for 366 cities in 10 countries in Latin America. The final dataset is a goldmine for health-related studies, as we now have a harmonised indicator for life expectancy across various population strata which is amenable to multi-country analysis at the city level. This complexity makes these data - and much of SALURBAL data - valuable but also makes the interaction between metadata (dimension tables) to the data (fact table) much more complex. The dimensional model for this dataset is shown below (Figure 8) and it requires four dimension tables:

- 1) The 'by_dataset' dimensional table which captures context on the dataset level includes some. Notice how compared to the simpler Air Pollution dataset fewer dimensional attributes (i.e., metadata fields) can be resolved at the dataset level.
- 2) The 'by_variable' dimensional table captures context at the variable level.
- 3) The 'by_var_iso2_year' dimensional table captures context about the original raw data sources which vary by country (iso2) and year.
- 4) The by_var_strata dimensional table captures information specific to each population strata such as decoding of strata coding into human understandable terms (e.g. Female, Age 10 years).

Figure 8. Entity relationship diagram for a SALURBAL dataset that has a more 'complex' harmonisation process.

3.3.3 Project level consumption - One Big Table

By implementing a flexible dimensional model for SALURBAL datasets, we have progressed through several key milestones:

- We have machine-actionable meta(data) at the data-point level within SALURBAL datasets
- Each dataset is rather standardised in terms of
 - Facts: what data attributes are collected
 - Fact Tables: how data attributes are structured
 - Dimensional Attributes: what metadata fields are collected.

But there is one still critical limitation, which is that the structure of dimension tables still varies by dataset. This is severely limiting as our metadata - while machine-actionable at the dataset level - is still not machine-actionable at the project level. This is a key hurdle to overcome because key information about data accessibility (whether a point can be accessed by the public or internal or specific individuals) lies at the data point level and not the dataset level. Without addressing this challenge, we cannot successfully implement FAIR (particularly the accessibility component) for SALURBAL.

To overcome this limitation, we leveraged another data modelling method: the One Big Table (OBT) technique which is (as discussed earlier) essentially a fact table that has all associated dimensional attributes denormalized (merged) as additional columns. By undergoing dataset-specific denormalization of the dimensional model into a One Big Table, we essentially abstract out from the equation the one incongruent aspect of our data model - the heterogeneity in the relationship between facts and dimensional attributes across datasets - thus enabling project-wide machine-actionability of both data and metadata at the data point level. In other words, by merging fact and dimension tables for each dataset we end up with many standardised One Big Table instances which can be easily joined to create a single One Big Table for the whole project; a simplified graph for this process is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Simplified graph of denormalization from dataset specific dimensional models to a project wide One Big Table (OBT).

As a reminder the project wide OBT is just all the data and facts merged into one table. This project-wide OBT can serve as a highly accessible single source of truth for all of the project's data

requirements such as data distribution, automated codebook generation, and development of analytic tools.

3.4 Implementation journey insights

Above we describe our top-down approach or the overall strategy for implementing FAIR in SALURBAL. However, the practical realisation of these principles requires a dedicated bottom-up effort that involves deviations from the plan, adapting to practical challenges, and iterative updates based on feedback. Here we discuss a few notable bottom-up insights.

3.4.1. Alignment on metadata ontology is a key step in FAIR implementation

One of the most dynamic aspects of our FAIR implementation was getting alignment from the SALURBAL team in regards to what metadata to collect. Our process involved a lot of iterating where the initial set of metadata fields were reviewed and updated based on conversations with domain experts. A notable point of discussion was the concept of a `variable_origin` metadata field, aimed at tracking the provenance of individual variables to establish a clear lineage. Although this idea initially seemed beneficial for administrative purposes and aligned with the FAIR principles, practical challenges quickly emerged. Many variables originated outside our inventory system, complicating the tracking of their provenance and inadvertently prioritising the ingestion of data that might not have otherwise been a priority. The lack of a comprehensive data provenance strategy further muddled our understanding of the extent to which we should trace back the origins of our data. Faced with these strategic challenges and time constraints, we ultimately decided not to pursue the detailed tracking of data provenance. However, future projects could consider utilisation of existing industry data provenance tools such as Data Built Tools to handle data provenance.

Through these discussions it became evident that the significance of metadata varies across projects and fields, emphasising the necessity for a pre-implementation phase dedicated to metadata ontology crafting. During this phase, domain experts convened to determine the crucial contextual information about our data and the relationships between this context and the data itself.

3.4.2. ETL pipelines for dimensional modelling data entry

Dimensional modelling presents challenges in data entry because data is stored more redundantly compared to normalized approaches. To address this, we implemented an Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) pipeline approach that utilised Jinja templating for managing redundant data entries efficiently. This method allows for the dynamic inclusion of data across multiple datasets through specific Jinja tags, streamlining the data entry process in complex scenarios. In a simplified example,

if we had a data source for population, we could - instead of filling out the source details for each dataset - utilise a tag such as `{{population}}`; our ETL pipeline has a compilation step that will detect and replace all Jinja tags appropriate key values which in this case would be population source information - see Figure 10. This approach provides a practical solution to the challenges posed by dimensional modelling, ensuring efficient data management within our ETL workflows.

Figure 10. Utilisation of Jinja templating to fill in information that is redundant across datasets.

The decision involves balancing the clarity of a more understandable data model against the necessity of integrating the logic for managing redundant data entries into an ETL system.

This decision was influenced not just by our existing familiarity with constructing flexible ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) pipelines but also by the specific challenges inherent to the project. These challenges include the complexity of data harmonisation and the variability in schemas across datasets. The utilisation of a rigid, normalized data modelling approach was deemed impractical for the SALURBAL project due to these challenges. Such an approach, while offering benefits in certain contexts such as ease of data entry, could lead to excessive complex schemas and a lack of flexibility in accommodating schema evolution, which is crucial for managing the diverse and evolving data sets within SALURBAL. Therefore, our strategy involves leveraging our ETL pipeline development capabilities to support more flexible and intuitive data models.

3.4.3 Harmonised datasets and FAIR Urban Health infrastructure

Harmonised datasets are powerful drivers of international Urban Health projects such as SALURBAL. However what makes these datasets unique and valuable - the harmonisation of complex raw data sets into a single dataset - is the same thing that makes it a particular challenge for FAIR implementation; how do we capture the metadata of these complex harmonisations in a FAIR

infrastructure? The key to unlocking the machine-actionability of harmonised datasets is to resolve meta(data) at the data point level through a combination of dataset-specific dimensional modelling, denormalization into project-wide One Big Table, and a flexible ETL pipeline to handle redundant data entries.

3.5 Deliverable update: SALURBAL Portal - a FAIR-enabling resource

One of the primary deliverables of the SALURBAL FIP was a website¹² that sits on top of our FAIR infrastructure which enables the public to access, interact and download publicly accessible SALURBAL data resources.

This section focuses on some FAIR features of this site and how they could be used to promote the findability and reusability of the SALURBAL resource.

3.5.1 SALURBAL Project data summary

Home / Data

About SALURBAL Data

Information about our data. To access the data catalog click [here](#).

The [SALURBAL](#) data resource is a comprehensive health and exposure dataset that covers [SALURBAL geographic units](#):

- 152,773,086 data points
- 560 variables categorized into 6 domains and 35 sub-domains
- 371 Latin American cities (L1)
- 1436 Latin American subcities (L2)
- 246,942 Latin American neighborhoods (L3)

Click [here](#) to access data catalog. Below you will find details about our data resource including: FAQs, variable categorization details, distribution of variables by domain/subdomain, distribution of data points by domain/subdomain.

DOMAINS VARIABLES DATA POINTS FAQ

Interactive table of SALURBAL domains and subdomains. Machine accessible [table here](#).

Demographics	This domain includes characteristics of the population of the area. These include overall number of people living in the area, age and sex of the population, birth rates, race and ethnic background and migration rates.	▼
Health Risk Factors	This domain includes health conditions, biomedical and behavioral risk factors that can affect overall well-being.	▼
Mortality	This domain includes measures of the rate at which people die as well as measures of life expectancy.	▼
Physical and Natural Environment	This domain includes environmental exposures as well as features of built and natural environments.	▼

Figure 11. SALURBAL Data webpage.

¹² <https://data.lacurbanhealth.org/>

This page includes some high-level metrics that our FAIR infrastructure was able to report. It also includes key information about our data such as how we categorise them, distribution of variables by domains, distribution of data points by domain and Frequently Asked Questions.

3.5.2 Data Catalog

We designed a user interface based on e-commerce websites. Users are given a similar interface where they can either use text searches or filter facets to find the variables they are interested in. Once they find it, they can click to go to a variable page to get details or click the “add to cart” button to add it to their cart.

Figure 12. SALURBAL data catalog page.

3.5.3 Variable details page

Each variable has a dedicated page where a project’s standardised metadata are displayed. These include variable level details but also more complex information. For example, below we can see the original data sources used for the harmonisation of this dataset.

Home / Data / Catalog / CNSWAH2

SOCIAL, ECONOMIC, AND SERVICES ENVIRONMENT GENDER EQUITY

Education Women’s achievement excluding countries without health care data

the variable captures factors related to women’s education standardized only to the countries where health care indicators are available. It includes 2 indicators: 1) % women ages 25+ with at least high school education, 2) % women ages 25+ with at least university education. This version uses the same variables as the Woman’s Achievements score 2 (CNSWA2L1AD) with the only difference being that this version creates Z scores for the score components using only the countries with health care data (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, and Mexico). This variable is created by standardizing education variables to the distribution of the L1ADs with health care measures available. Women’s achievement scores were derived from a principle components analysis.

Variable ID: CNSWAH2
Dataset ID: wescores

ADD TO CART

DETAILS DATA SOURCES STRATA DETAILS DATA AVAILABILITY DATA PREVIEW

ISO2	Year	Source
AR	2014-2016	(census) Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (INDEC), Argentina
BR	2014-2016	(census) Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística (IBGE), Brazil
CL	2014-2016	(census) Instituto Nacional de Estadísticas (INE), Chile
MX	2014-2016	(census) Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía (INEGI), México

Figure 13. Variable details overview webpage.

3.5.4 Data checkout page

After users have selected the data they are interested in, there is a checkout process that then allows them to specify various attributes of the data to refine their data extract request and then to fill out a form to collect usage information. Once users submit this request, the SALURBAL system will generate an analytic dataset with the data requested and email it to them.

HOME DATA PRODUCTS ABOUT English

Home / Data / Checkout

Data Checkout

Fill out the form below to complete your data download request.

- ✓ Review Cart
- ✓ Select geographic level
- ✓ Select countries
- 4 Checkout Details

Order/Request Name (e.g. 'ms893 analytic dataset')

Full Name Email

Institution Sector Primary Data use(s)

Additional Information

Figure 14. Data checkout webpage.

3.5.5 SALURBAL products catalog

In addition to data, this platform tries to expand FAIR into non-data-related artefacts of research. Our team called these 'products' which include publications and interactive digital content. The long-term goal is to be able to link data to these products and thus be able to utilise FAIR infrastructure to engage with not just a data-oriented audience but a much more diverse set of stakeholders involved in urban health.

Figure 15. Products catalog webpage.

3.6 Future plans

3.6.1 Early implementation of FAIR infrastructure for urban health projects

Implementing FAIR principles in the SALURBAL project presented significant challenges, particularly in retrofitting these standards onto legacy data infrastructures. The task was complicated by the absence of original data contributors, leading to difficulties in understanding and managing historical datasets. This experience underscores the importance of embedding FAIR principles at the outset of data collection efforts to ensure smoother future integrations. Our team looks forward to implementing this early on in future urban health projects such as SALURBAL-Climate, a 5-year

extension of SALURBAL as well as within the Drexel Climate Change and Urban Health Research Center.

3.6.2 Integration of FAIR infrastructure with existing data provenance tools

One of the key aspects of the FIP we want to develop further is data provenance infrastructure - or tracking meta(data) as it goes through layers of transformation. There are industry workflows such as Data Built Tools (DBT) to build well-organised data warehouses but these are not commonly utilised in academic settings. In the future, we hope to explore the integration feasibility between the data provenance systems (e.g., DBT) and a FAIR meta(data) inventory (e.g., the SALURBAL FIP). Such integrations could bridge the existing data stewardship gaps to enable a more comprehensive implementation of the FAIR principles in research infrastructure. It is also of interest to explore how such integrations could export FAIR provenance file formats.

3.6.3 Integration into the global FAIR ecosystem

The focus of the SALURBAL FIP was building a high level of FAIR infrastructure locally, particularly because we had to demonstrate clear analytic and administrative value of having FAIR infrastructure to the organisation's leadership. However, the long-term goal of SALURBAL is to be integrated into the larger global FAIR ecosystem, specifically by adopting the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) Standards. We have updated our original online FIP proposal¹³ - specifically the Interoperability and Reusability points - to reflect this, as follows:

- **Interoperability:**
 - **I1:** DDI uses XML for representation of metadata which is a widely used standard for encoding documents in a manner that is human-readable and machine-readable. This supports interoperability and allows SALURBAL metadata to be integrated and utilised by various data systems.
 - **I2:** DDI provides standardised vocabularies for describing data in social, behavioural, and economics sciences. Adhering to these controlled vocabularies increases interoperability, making it easier for researchers to standardise terms across studies and disciplines.
 - **I3:** DDI allows references to other datasets supporting linkages between related datasets and capturing data relationships. This aspect of DDI can support the integration of data from various sources.
- **Reusable:**

¹³ <https://drexel-uhc.github.io/salurbal-project-dashboard/>

- **R1:** DDI enables the documentation of a wide range of attributes for each dataset, including study design, sampling methodology, data collection procedures, variable definitions, and coding schemes.
- **R1.1:** All publicly accessible SALURBAL data will be under a CC BY 4.0 License.
- **R1.2:** DDI captures detailed provenance information, including the origin of the data, the methodology used to collect it, and any transformations or analyses the data has undergone.
- **R1.3:** DDI itself is a community standard developed for and by the research community in the social, behavioural, and economic sciences. It reflects the specific needs and practices of this community, ensuring that metadata and data are documented in a way that meets domain-relevant expectations.

4. Recommendations

We present six summarised recommendations based on our findings from the training component (Part 1) of this Deliverable. Each recommendation is assigned a type¹⁴ and an audience.

1. **Enhance Academic Engagement in FAIR/CARE principles:** Academic researchers and institutions of higher education should develop targeted advocacy materials to underscore the relevance of FAIR and CARE principles, particularly emphasising the requirements from funding bodies like the NIH to ensure broader participation in future training activities. Engage in conversations with key academic stakeholders to better understand barriers to the adoption of FAIR/CARE principles. **Type: Organisational.**
2. **Establish Continuous Learning and Community Support:** Institutions of higher education should establish a sustainable platform for continuous learning and discussion, such as a dedicated online forum or slack (or similar) channel, to maintain engagement and provide ongoing support beyond the duration of training activities. To maintain engagement, a clear value proposition must be made, so that participants see value in engaging in these activities. This proposition can include the sharing of resources, or even mandates by funders (as NIH is starting to do). This is aimed at data practitioners, both in academic and non-academic settings. **Type: Organisational.**
3. **Integrate Practical Application Examples:** Data practitioners should integrate more concrete, real-world examples of FAIR and CARE principles in the training materials to better illustrate their application in urban health research, thereby enabling participants to operationalize these concepts in their daily work. For example, integrating our own FAIR Implementation Profile and the resulting SALURBAL Platform could help trainees understand the need for FAIR/CARE principles. **Type: Organisational; Technical (data and metadata).**
4. **Encourage Cross-Domain Integration:** Data practitioners should encourage cross-disciplinary collaboration by creating engagement activities that address the application of FAIR and CARE principles in large-scale, cross-domain projects, promoting a more holistic approach to data management across diverse research fields. Projects such as WorldFAIR can be instrumental in achieving this. Funders could also be instrumental by including mandates to engage in these efforts. **Type: Organisational; Policy.**
5. **Provide Customised Content and Resources:** Institutions of higher education should tailor the training content to meet the specific needs of different audiences, including community

¹⁴ Policy, Legal, Organisational, Technical (data); or Technical (metadata).

practitioners, data scientists, and public health officials, ensuring that the material is relevant and actionable for each group. **Type: Organisational.**

6. **Develop a Community of Practice:** Data practitioners should foster a community of practice by organising regular roundtables, webinars, and interviews with data stewards and leaders in urban health, thereby creating a collaborative environment for sharing best practices and experiences. Our second activity of the first part of this deliverable, with several engagement activities, aims to achieve this. **Type: Organisational.**

Moreover, and based on our updated FAIR Implementation Profile (Part 2 of this Deliverable), we present five recommendations:

1. **Enhance Data Engineering Education and Skills:** Higher education institutions and other learning organisations should invest in training programs focused on data engineering within urban health research teams, emphasising the importance of data modelling, ETL pipeline construction, and management of complex data systems. Encourage cross-disciplinary learning to ensure all team members have a fundamental understanding of data engineering concepts. **Type: Organisational and policy.**
2. **Develop Flexible Data Models:** Data practitioners should adopt a hybrid approach to data modelling that utilises both One Big Table and Dimensional Modelling to balance accessibility with analytical needs, ensuring that complex datasets can be efficiently used by a diverse range of end-users. Design data models that can be easily adapted as new data sources and structures emerge, with a focus on scalability and interoperability. **Type: Technical (data).**
3. **Improve Metadata Management and Provenance:** Data practitioners should establish a comprehensive metadata ontology early in the data collection process, with input from domain experts to ensure all relevant contextual information is captured. Develop a systematic approach for tracking data provenance, potentially integrating with industry-standard tools like Data Built Tools (DBT), to enhance data integrity and traceability. **Type: Technical (metadata).**
4. **Promote FAIR Principles Globally:** Data practitioners should align project data management strategies with international standards such as the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI), to facilitate global interoperability and reusability of data. utilise controlled vocabularies and standardised metadata formats to ensure that datasets can be easily understood and integrated across various research domains. Funders should also consider mandates that promote the use of FAIR principles (e.g., NIH and the new data management plans). **Type: Organisational and policy.**

- 5. Foster Community Engagement and Collaboration:** Data practitioners and learning institutions should create and nurture communities of practice that bring together researchers, practitioners, and data scientists to share insights, challenges, and strategies related to FAIR and CARE principles in urban health data management. Leverage online platforms, workshops, and symposiums to disseminate knowledge, gather feedback, and collaboratively refine data management practices. This connects directly to the first part of this deliverable. **Type: Organisational.**

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6. Appendix: Materials involved in Deliverable 8.2

6.1 Workshop structure

6.1.1 Course schedule

Day 1	
Asynchronous - before sync session	Introduction to FAIR principles
	Be FAIR and CARE
	NIH and other organizations' requirements for Data Management Plans
	Presentation of SALURBAL and WorldFAIR projects
Sync 1.1: Intro and async recap (2:30 - 3:00 pm)	Introductions (20 minutes) Minute paper (5 minutes)
Sync 1.2: Practical FAIR - Big Picture template DMS (3:00 - 4:00 pm)	<p>Practical:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NIH DMS Key concepts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Things not strings: Orchid - Controlled vocabulary - Shared Ontology - Collect FAIR metadata with CEDAR Workbench (https://metadatacenter.org/) - CEDAR to repository - utilise industry tools to integrated metadata and data <p>Discussion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discuss with students to see what deliverable they would like to build on day 5 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Urban Health Ontology
Day 2	
Asynchronous - before sync	FAIR case study 1: SALURBAL FAIR implementation profile

session	FAIR case study 2: SALURBAL survey harmonization
	FAIR case study 3: SALURBAL race/ ethnicity screening of data in health information sources
Sync 2.1: Async recap (1:00 - 1:15 pm)	Comments and discussion on day 1
Sync 2.2 Exercise: craft and deploy a urban health specific ontology (1:15 - 2:15 pm)	Tools: - Sheets2rdf - OntoStack
Asynchronous- End-day Activity (2.15 - 2.30 pm)	Share your own case study/ experience (if you have it) in the discussion board
Day 3	
Asynchronous - before sync session	Introduction to CARE principles
	Indigenous Data Sovereignty: Origins of CARE principles
	CARE case study: SALURBAL data handling of live births
	Challenges around CARE
Sync 3.1: Async recap (1:00 - 1:15 pm)	Comments and discussion on day 2
Sync 3.2 Exercise: Collect FAIR metadata with CEDAR workbench (1:15 - 2:15 pm)	Tools: - CEDAR Workbench (https://metadatacenter.org/) - Deposit FAIR Metadata from CEDAR into a repository
Asynchronous- End-day Activity (2.15 - 2.30 pm)	Share your own challenges with CARE in the discussion board
Day 4	
Asynchronous - before sync	6 key principles for building trust in data and community

session	Building Trust in data in Urban and Public Health
	Data sovereignty and legitimacy: a New Zealand example
Sync 4.1: Async recap (1:00 - 1:15 pm)	Comments and discussion on day 3
Sync 4.2 Exercise: Industry solutions (1:15 - 2:30 pm)	Transition to Industry Solutions Tools: - Github - DBT
Day 5	
Asynchronous - before sync session	Integration of FAIR and CARE within your context. Limitations of real context
	FAIR and CARE on the 'edges': - Data in contexts of crisis/ emergency - Other challenges
	Comments and discussion on day 4
Sync 5.1 Exercise: Wrapping it up DMP (1:00 - 2:00 pm)	- Wrap up remaining tasks - Deploy to Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) Deliverable: - template DMS - hands on experience with ORCID
Sync 5.2: Async recap (2:00 - 2:30 pm)	Conclusions- Course perception/ feedback
Asynchronous- End-day Activity	Post- course survey

6.1.2 Pre-course survey

Dear participants:

DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Thank you for your interest in the course “*How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and good practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/ public health*”.

Before starting the course, we would like to know more about the expectations that participants have for this course. This brief, anonymous survey, which will not take more than 15 minutes to complete, will help us to accommodate the contents of the course to your needs.

For us it would be very useful if the majority of the participants could complete this survey. If you decide to answer it, once you finish, we would appreciate it if you could encourage other participants to complete it as well.

We hope this course will be a lot of shared learning!
See you soon,

Ran, Ana, and Theresa

Tell us a bit about you...

1. What is your role and your organization (affiliation and position)?

0. Would you be able to attend synchronous activities in person or remotely?
 - o In person
 - o Remotely
 - o Either way

0. What motivated you to enroll in this course?

0. What would you like to have accomplished by the end of this course?

Now a bit about data and work...

1. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is very infrequent or unlikely and 5 is very likely and frequent, please tell us about your everyday work

	1	2	3	4	5
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I work in the creation of instruments and guidelines for primary data collection					
I collect, process, and consolidate data from secondary sources					
I train personnel in the release of surveys and questionnaires					
I work in the community collecting data					
I use data for monitoring and research					
I have responsibility for stewarding data within my organisation					
I have responsibility for stewarding data by liaising with the communities from whom the data is collected					

0. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest level of knowledge and experience and 5 is the highest level, please indicate the level of knowledge and familiarity you have regarding the following ideas.

	1	2	3	4	5
FAIR principles					
CARE principles					
Metadata schemas					
Metadata preservation policies					
Identifier services					

0. Can you give an example of your everyday work when you face challenges with using/handling data?

0. Is there anything else you would like us to know?

6.1.3 Post-course Survey

Dear participants:

Thank you for your participation in the course “*How to create a data management plan with CARE and FAIR: introduction to essential concepts and good practices in data management and sharing for researchers and practitioners in urban/ public health*”.

For us it was a pleasure sharing time and experiences with you over this week, and we look forward to keeping connected with you through different channels.

We kindly ask you if you could complete this post- course survey. It would help us to improve and refine the content of this course for future iterations.

We hope this course has been helpful to you!
See you soon,

Ran, Ana, and Theresa

After these 5 days of intensive learning about FAIR and CARE principles...

1. Were you able to accomplish what motivated you to enrol in this course? Tell us how and why.

0. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest level of knowledge and experience and 5 is the highest level, please indicate the level of knowledge and familiarity you have regarding the following ideas

	1	2	3	4	5
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FAIR principles					
CARE principles					
Metadata schemas					
Metadata preservation policies					
Identifier services					

0. Is there anything else you would like us to know?

6.2 Workshop content

To download the workshop content (slides, recordings and other materials) please follow this link: <https://zenodo.org/records/10231138>.

6.3 Data Engineering glossary

- **Apache Parquet:** Apache Parquet is a robust storage format, akin to CSV but far more suited for modern analytics. Parquet's columnar storage format is key to its effectiveness, particularly in saving storage space. By organising data by column rather than row, Parquet can store information more compactly. This is because columns of the same data type tend to have similar values, which can be more efficiently compressed using various encoding schemes. Such storage efficiency is not just about saving space; it also means less data to read during queries, speeding up data retrieval. For analytics, where performance and storage cost are paramount, Parquet's approach offers significant advantages, making it an optimal choice for managing and analysing large datasets.
- **Data Engineering:** A field focused on enabling efficient analytics by designing data models and effectively implementing those designs with the appropriate infrastructure. It

encompasses the management of data flows from raw form to end-users, utilising relational databases, distributed systems, or cloud infrastructure to facilitate data access, processing, and analysis.

- **Data Grain:** The most detailed level at which data is captured within a dataset. It specifies the scope or level of detail represented by a single record in a data model. For example, in a healthcare context, the data grain might be "a single patient visit to a healthcare facility," with each record representing one instance of a patient's visit, including all relevant details.
- **Data Modelling:** The process of creating a structured representation of an organisation's data, detailing how different pieces of information are interconnected and flow within a system. This involves defining how data is stored, organised, and accessed, typically visualised through diagrams such as Entity-Relationship Diagrams (ERD).
- **Denormalization:** A strategy that merges data from multiple tables into one, increasing redundancy to improve query performance. It simplifies data retrieval at the cost of larger storage requirements and potential complications in data maintenance due to repeated information.
- **Dimension Tables:** Accompanying fact tables in dimensional modelling, dimension tables contain descriptive attributes or metadata that provide context for the data captured in fact tables. These tables include dimensions such as time, geography, or other characteristics that enable detailed and multifaceted analysis of the facts.
- **Fact Tables:** In dimensional modelling, fact tables are the central tables that contain the quantitative metrics or actual data points used for analysis. Each row in a fact table represents an instance of an event or transaction, with metrics such as numerical values or counts that can be analysed.
- **One Big Table (OBT):** A data modelling technique that consolidates all relevant data into a single table, prioritising simplicity and accessibility for end-users. This approach is characterised by storing data in a wide format, where each row is a record, and all information about that record is stored within the row. This method simplifies data access but may lead to redundancy.
- **Normalisation:** The process of organising data into separate tables to minimise redundancy and improve integrity. This method ensures each piece of data is stored only once, reducing storage needs and simplifying updates, but may require complex queries to gather related information.